

Schmidt Ocean Institute Post Expedition Report

Ultra Fine-Scale Seafloor Mapping

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1 Overview

SOI Expedition ID	FKt231025
Vessel	R/V <i>Falkor (too)</i>
Expedition Name	Ultra Fine-Scale Seafloor Mapping
Expedition Dates	2023/10/25 - 2023/11/23
Departure Port	Golfito, Costa Rica
Termination Port	Balboa, Panama
Ocean	South Pacific Ocean

Map of Expedition Location

Figure 1: Map of Expedition Location.

1.1 Expedition Overview

Seafloor mapping is integral to oceanographic research. Bathymetric maps illustrate the seafloor’s depth, contours, and physical features, and they are often used as the first essential step in planning a successful submersible operation. Multibeam sonar, the typical tool used to collect data, is then processed to create a three-dimensional topographical outline of the seafloor. Physical hardware limitations can hamper the resolution of the data, and cannot fully reveal important details of the seafloor. A ground-breaking technology was tested on this expedition that can collect high-resolution data.

On this expedition, the capabilities of a sonar system new to scientific seafloor mapping, Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Sonar (InSAS), were tested. This technology combines bathymetric data collected from sonars with acoustic imagery (“photographs” created by sound instead of light) and is capable of capturing unmatched resolution fine enough to depict individual animals dwelling on the seafloor. InSAS collects the data in exceptionally high resolution by using software advances to overcome hardware limitations. It combines two key capabilities of traditional sonar systems: the detailed top-down imaging of sidescan sonar and the bathymetry collected by a multibeam echo sounder. However, its much higher resolution, up to 3 centimeters, is drastically better than the typical 50-meter resolution of ship-based sonar systems, which are intended for gathering large swaths of data rather than ultrafine details. The resolution is also better than the 50 cm to 1 meter resolution of AUV-based multibeam systems, also often used to collect data on the seafloor.

Traditional sonar systems emit a ping and measure the return with a receiver. Rather than adhering to this “ping-and-listen” pattern, InSAS emits pings continuously, painting the seafloor with sound beams, and simulates a synthetic physical receiver using software. The result is exceptionally high-resolution imagery that can then be used for surveying, characterizing, and exploring the deep seafloor in a novel way. While InSAS has been previously available for military and industrial applications, it has had limited application in the research sciences. The research team on *Falkor (too)* deployed InSAS over hydrothermal vent fields of the Eastern Galapagos Spreading Center and assessed its potential as a revolutionary seafloor mapping tool.

1.2 Authorizations and Permitting

Permit Number	Permit Authority	Permit Focus
DIRNEA-SNA-No.019-2023	Armada del Ecuador	Entry for scientific purposes of the vessel <i>Falkor (too)</i>
MAATE-DPNG/DGA-2023-1543-O	Parque Nacional Galapagos Ecuador	Field research in Galapagos National Park

1.3 Expedition Timeline

The expedition commenced on October 25, 2023, departing from Golfito, Costa Rica, and ended in Balboa, Panama, on November 23, 2023.

1.4 Expedition Objectives

The expedition had two main objectives: to evaluate and develop interferometric synthetic aperture sonar (InSAS) as a tool for seafloor exploration, classification, and monitoring, and to investigate the evolution of hydrothermal vents in the region, particularly after they become inactive or extinct.

2 Expedition Accomplishments

2.1 At-sea Accomplishments

2.1.1 Science

During this expedition, using InSAS enabled the team to locate seafloor features with greater accuracy and produce detailed, high-resolution maps. Combining bathymetric data from multibeam sonar with acoustic imagery gathered by InSAS, the team generated what the researchers liken to a photograph created with sound instead of light. This technology will transform the ability to map, explore, classify, and monitor the seafloor environment in extremely high detail, and dramatically reduce the time needed to investigate and locate seafloor features.

Using InSAS, the science team imaged individual seafloor features, such as pillows, chimneys, and faults — features that would not be identifiable in traditional high-resolution multibeam data collected by the vessel (Figure 2). Using the data collected by InSAS, the scientists could determine whether the hydrothermal vents were active or inactive by visualizing the thermal distortion caused by the hot fluids. The InSAS data led scientists to discover several active and inactive venting sites on the seafloor, exceeding exploration and sampling expectations for the expedition. Ultimately, the researchers believe InSAS will become a powerful tool for gathering data on seafloor features. The science team hopes to prove this tool's usefulness and scale its use for future government and scientific exploration.

Figure 2: Geological features imaged using InSAS

The team discovered a new vent field, named “Tortugas” (in reference to the famous Galapagos tortoises) (Figure 3). The vent field is located on the rim of the Los Huellos East caldera, within the Galapagos Marine Reserve. The vents were initially identified from features mapped with the ROV-based M3 sonar. In addition to the discovery of Tortugas, several other previously undocumented active hydrothermal vents were discovered, as well as numerous inactive / extinct vent sites along the Galapagos Rift. Overall, the team demonstrated the advantages of combined ROV M3/InSAS mapping followed by exploration and sampling for efficient seafloor exploration.

Figure 3: Venting of clear fluids at the newly-discovered Tortugas vent field.

The team identified and recorded several previously undocumented vent-associated species in this region (see details below). In addition, the team collected skate eggs from one of only two known Pacific white skate (*Bathyraja spinosissima*) nurseries, providing a unique opportunity to investigate genetic connectivity and the association of the nurseries with active hydrothermal venting.

The extensive sampling of rocks, fluids, sediments, and animals from a wide range of different active and inactive vent fields along the Galapagos Spreading Center will provide excellent datasets for studying the geological and ecological evolutions of hydrothermal venting along the Galapagos Rift and the relationships between vent-associated ecosystems and geological processes.

Figure 4: Collection of a skate egg casing near a hydrothermal vent.

Finally, hydrophone lander deployments recorded the soundscape at active hydrothermal vent fields, recording audio data from venting processes as well as animals (e.g., snapping sounds from crabs). The audio recordings will also provide insights into noise generated by the research vessel and the ROV at the seafloor.

2.2 Post-Expedition Activities and Accomplishments

2.2.1 Overview

The data and samples collected during the expedition form the basis for many different research projects.

Mapping: In addition to their utility for ROV dive planning and exploration, the multibeam sonar mapping and magnetometer datasets are being used to generate geological maps of the Galapagos Spreading Center, using remote predictive mapping approaches.

Rocks: The volcanic and hydrothermal rock samples collected during the expedition will form the basis of several studies to understand the geological controls on hydrothermal venting along the Galapagos Spreading Center and the mineralogical and geochemical evolution of inactive / extinct hydrothermal vents. Samples will undergo a full suite of geochemical and mineralogical analyses.

Animals: Animals will be identified (down to the species level when possible), and in some cases, stable isotope analyses will be performed (to investigate food chains). Animal distributions will be analyzed in a spatial context (using bathymetric maps, InSAR backscatter imagery, and ROV-based video and photogrammetry reconstructions) to investigate their relationships to hydrothermal venting and other geological processes at the seafloor.

Microbes: Genetic analyses will be performed to identify microbial species living on active and inactive hydrothermal vents.

Sediments: Sediments collected with push cores will be analyzed using a suite of mineralogical and geochemical techniques, including Raman spectroscopy for characteristics such as grain size, presence of total nitrogen, total organic and inorganic carbon, carbon isotopes (including radiocarbon), amino acids and lipid biomarkers

Waters: Porewater samples will be analyzed for nutrients and trace metal contents, and total mercury. Seawater samples will be analyzed for ultra trace metal concentrations, and Sr, U, and Mo isotopes.

Acoustics: The acoustic data collected by Dalhousie University's hydrophone lander will be used to characterize the natural soundscapes at and near hydrothermal vents. The data will also be used to assess the amount of noise generated by both surface vessels and underwater vehicles.

Overall, these combined datasets and analyses will provide insights into the combined geological and ecological characteristics of the Galapagos Spreading Center, how these characteristics compare to other regions in the Pacific Ocean, and how they vary along the Galapagos Spreading Center. This information is critical to our understanding of the

importance of hydrothermal systems and associated ecosystems to the benthic environment, the diversity of these features and processes at both a local and global scale, and most importantly, their vulnerability. The outcomes of this project, especially the results of the InSAS surveys, will lead to improved approaches to seafloor characterization and monitoring, which are critical for developing effective environmental management plans for, e.g., Marine Protected Areas.

2.2.2 New Discoveries

The discoveries, including a new high-temperature vent field, reveal insights into the distribution of hydrothermal vents along mid-ocean ridges and the distribution of organisms along those vents, which vary among the age of the vent and the amount of venting. As a result, scientists will better understand how these thriving communities evolve once a vent field ceases to be active.

The newly discovered "Tortugas" vent field is located at the base of the western wall, where it is cut by the axial faults of the central Galapagos Rift between the East and West Los Huellos calderas. The field consists of several clusters of tall (up to 12 m high) sulfide-rich chimneys, many venting clear fluids, and abundant tube worms. The maximum recorded vent fluid temperature was 274°C. Vent fluids were clear and generally emanating from focused spire orifices. Rock and microbial samples were collected from the active vents, mainly from small chimneys (especially beehive structures) on the flanks and tops of the larger spires. A second field of inactive spires was located on the east caldera wall, where it is intersected by the rift faults.

Additionally, the team observed upwards of 15 species previously not known to live in the region and two that are likely new to science, which are still being validated scientifically. The team identified and collected an extremely rare "living fossil" monoplacophoran mollusc *Neopilina galathea*, from a basaltic substrate near the Rose Garden vent field (Figure 5). This discovery represents a southern range extension for this species, and one of the very few specimens ever collected *in situ*.

Figure 5: Image of a monoplacophoran mollusc *Neopilina galatheae*, a “living fossil”, on basaltic substrate.

The scientists also discovered a Pacific White Skate nursery associated with hydrothermal vents. This is only the second documented nursery for the Pacific White Skate. In total, 39 egg cases were collected over three dives, two at the Iguanas and one at Pinguinos vents. Of those egg cases collected, 24 contained material for possible genetic testing. It was observed that the egg cases change in color over time (i.e., as the embryo develops): bright yellow egg cases were new, and often contained only yoke, while dark brown egg cases (with or without holes, colored staining, white patches) were often “empty” (no embryo or only decaying remains).

2.2.3 Software Utilized

Specialized software was used to process various components of the data from the mapping operations performed during the expedition. Initial cleaning of both ship- and ROV-based multibeam sonar data was completed using QIMERA v8.6.0. InSAS data was processed using Kraken Robotics’ in-house software INSIGHT v13.1 as well as Caris HIPS and SIPS v11.4.

2.3 Data

Datasets acquired during this expedition and those derived from the analysis of collected data and samples as of this report's publication date.

Data Type	Curator	Status
Vessel underway data (CTD, Multibeam, sonar, etc)	Rolling Deck to Repository	Completed
ADCP	University of Hawaii Data Acquisition System	Completed
Data collected by ROV <i>SuBastian</i> , including navigation, acoustic backscatter, conductivity, oxygen, temperature and photography, magnetometer	Marine Geoscience Data System (MGDS)	Completed
Rock samples, metadata, and their International Geosample Numbers (IGSN)	Zenodo	Completed
Genetic Sequence		In progress
Miniature Autonomous Plume Recorder data		In progress
Fauna species data		In progress
Biological samples		In progress

Table 1. List of all publicly available data

2.4 Publications

Current publications as of the date of this report's publication.

Chen, Chong. 2024. "In Situ Observation and Range Extension of the First Discovered Monoplacophoran *Neopilina Galathea*." bioRxiv. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2023.11.08.566290>.

Chen, Chong, John W. Jamieson, and Verena Tunnicliffe. 2024. "Hydrothermal Vent Fauna of the Galápagos Rift: Updated Species List with New Records." *Marine Biodiversity* 54 (2): 16. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12526-024-01408-w>.

Jamieson, John W., Caroline Gini, Craig Brown, and Katleen Robert. n.d. "Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Sonar: A New Tool for Seafloor Characterization | Oceanography." Accessed June 30, 2025. <https://tos.org/oceanography/article/interferometric-synthetic-aperture-sonar-a-new-tool-for-seafloor-characterization>.

Li, Yunlong, Xu Liu, Chong Chen, Jian-Wen Qiu, Kevin Kocot, and Jin Sun. 2025. "Reliable Inference of Phylogenomic Relationship via Assembly-Based Strategy Accommodating Raw Reads and Proteins." bioRxiv. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.07.24.604968>.

3 Appendix

3.1 Science Party Information

Scientists aboard R/V *Falkor (too)*:

Scientist	Institution
John Jamieson	Memorial University in Newfoundland
Erin Bethell	University of Ottawa
Carlos Braga	University of Ottawa
Craig Brown	Dalhousie University
Chong Chen	Japan Agency for Marine-Earth Science and Technology
Cherisse Du Preez	Fisheries and Oceans Canada
Maria Figueroa	United States Geological Survey
Chris Galley	University of Ottawa
Caroline Gini	Memorial University of Newfoundland
Mark Hannington	University of Ottawa
Moronke Harris	University of Victoria
Hope Ianiri	United States Geological Survey
Charles Lapointe	Memorial University of Newfoundland
Sarah Moriarty	Memorial University of Newfoundland
Monika Neufeld	Dalhousie University
Brendan Smith	Dalhousie University
Jake Tan	Dalhousie University
Verena Tunnicliffe	University of Victoria

Shore-based Scientists contributing to the expedition:

Scientist	Institution
Amy Gartman	Amy Gartman
Stephanie Kusch	University of Quebec, Rimouski
Andre Pellerin	University of Quebec, Rimouski
Jacob Tidwell	University of California, Santa Cruz
Evan Edinger	Memorial University of Newfoundland
Maurice Tivey	Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution
Amanda Bates	University of Victoria
Kim Juniper	University of Victoria

Coastal State Observers:

Name	Institution
Ana Belén Yáñez Suárez	Charles Darwin Foundation
Diego Gernando Bermeo Guambo	Parc Nacional Galápagos)
Richard Narera Ortega	INOCAR

Artist at Sea: Elana Alonso Fernández

3.2 Conferences, Presentations, and Posters

Chong Chen, "Fantastic hydrothermal vent beasts and how to protect them" 2024/03
Invited Oral at the 71st Annual Meeting of the Ecological Society of Japan Yokohama
National University, Japan

Ianiri, H. L., Prouty, N. G., Gartman, A., Campbell, P. L., (2025). Comparing organic carbon cycling across diverse hydrothermal marine mineral systems. Ocean Carbon and Biogeochemistry Workshop, Virtual. Invited talk.

Ianiri, H. L., Prouty, N. G., Gartman, A., Campbell, P. L., (2025). Assessing chemical fingerprints of organic carbon cycling in hydrothermal marine mineral sediments. Chemical Oceanography Gordon Conference, Manchester, NH. Poster.

Neufeld, M., Metaxas, A., Meyn, K. (2024). Mapping the distribution of non-vent-obligate megafauna at active hydrothermal vent fields. Oral Presentation (GEOHAB 2024 - Habitat Mapping for Sustainable Oceans, Arendal, NO: International).

Daniel K.C. Ng, Cherisse Du Preez, John W. Jamieson, Craig J. Brown. (2025). High-resolution mapping of Pacific white skate (*Bathyrāja spinosissima*) nursery habitats at an active Galápagos hydrothermal vent field. GeoHab conference, Key West, Florida. 12-16 May, 2025. Oral Presentation. Ron McDowell Scholarship recipient.

Daniel K.C. Ng, Cherisse Du Preez, John W. Jamieson, Craig J. Brown. (2025). High-resolution mapping of Pacific white skate (*Bathyrāja spinosissima*) nursery habitats at an active Galápagos hydrothermal vent field. Biology and Applied Aquatic Sciences (BAAS) Conference 2025. Acadia University, Wolfville, Nova Scotia. March 7-9, 2025. Poster presentation.

Daniel K.C. Ng, Cherisse Du Preez, John W. Jamieson, Craig J. Brown. (2025). High-resolution mapping of Pacific white skate (*Bathyrāja spinosissima*) nursery habitats at an active Galápagos hydrothermal vent field. Biology and Applied Aquatic Sciences (BAAS) Conference 2025. CDOGS - Annual Conference of Dalhousie Oceanography Graduate Students. Dalhousie University, Halifax, Nova Scotia. April 11, 2025. Poster presentation.

Gini, C., Brown, C.J., Robert, K., Jamieson, J. W. (2025). Fine-scale mapping of lava flows along the Galapagos Spreading Center using interferometric synthetic aperture sonar. GeoHab '25). Key West, USA, May 11-16, 2025.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11086164>

Gini, C., Jamieson, J. W., Robert, K., Brown, C.J., Galley, C.G., & Rubin, J. (2024). Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Sonar for centimeter scale mapping and imaging of seafloor hydrothermal deposits and lava flows, Galapagos Rift, Pacific Ocean. In Harris, P. T., Thorsnes, T., Dolan, M., & Bjarnadóttir, L. R. Proceedings of the 2024 International Symposium on Marine Geological and Biological Habitat Mapping (GeoHab '24). Arendal, Norway, May 6-10, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11086164>

Galley, C., Jamieson, J.W., Tivey, M., Hannington, M.D., Bethell, E., Baxter, A.T., and Fornari, D.J. 2024. A Time-Series Magnetic and Bathymetric Analysis of Volcanism and Hydrothermal Alteration at the Rose Garden and Rosebud Hydrothermal Vent Fields, Galapagos Rift. Poster presentation at the AGU 2024 Fall Meeting in Washington D.C., USA.

Special session at the AGU 2024 Fall Meeting in Washington D.C., USA: “Linking Magmatic, Tectonic, and Hydrothermal Processes in Arc-Back-Arc and Mid-Ocean Ridge Settings”. Convened by Galley, C., Baxter, A.T., Hannington, M.D., Jamieson, J.W., and Bethell, E.

Special session at the GAC-MAC-IAH-CNC 2025 Meeting in Ottawa, Canada: “Advances in Marine Geology and Geodynamics and their Application to Understanding Ancient Metallogenic Terranes”. Convened by Baxter, A.T., Bethell, E., Galley, C., and Hannington, M.D.

3.3 Student Projects, Theses, and Dissertations

Brendan Smith: PhD thesis: "Soundscapes of hydrothermal vent fields" (Dalhousie University)

Monika Neufeld: PhD thesis: "Mapping the distribution of non-vent-obligate megafauna at active hydrothermal vent fields" (Dalhousie University)

Carlos Braga: PhD thesis: "Geological controls on hydrothermal venting along the Galapagos Rift" (University of Ottawa)

Moronke Harris: PhD thesis: "Microbial landscape modelling for the evaluation of genetic resources associated with seafloor hydrothermal deposits" (University of Victoria)

Caroline Gini: PhD thesis: "Interferometric synthetic aperture sonar as a tool for geological mapping of the seafloor" (Memorial University of Newfoundland)

Sarah Moriarty: PhD thesis: "Sulfur isotopes as tracers of endmember interactions and evolution of seafloor hydrothermal systems" (Memorial University of Newfoundland)

Jake Tan: PhD thesis: "Artificial intelligence techniques applied to ocean mapping using remote sensing data" (Dalhousie University)

Daniel Ng: Honours Thesis: "High-resolution mapping of Pacific white skate (*Bathyraja spinosissima*) nursery habitats at an active Galápagos hydrothermal vent field in Iguanas-Pinguinos" (Dalhousie University)

Martin, F.: B.Sc. Honours thesis: "Volcanic and Structural Dynamics of the Galápagos Rift Transform Fault System: Implications for Mid-Ocean Ridge Tectonics and Magmatism" (University of Ottawa)

3.4 Cruise Records

- [Cruise Logs](#).
- ROV *SuBastian* [Dive List](#).

3.5 Media

Fukamedia, Japan: "We asked JAMSTEC's Dr. Chen about the real Galápagos — the stage for the discovery of hydrothermal vents and the birth of evolutionary theory."
<https://www.fukamedia.jp/jamstec-galapagos/>

Canadian Geographic: “Wonder and loss: the deep ocean and its future”
<https://canadiangeographic.ca/articles/wonder-and-loss-the-deep-ocean-and-its-future/>

Ocean Frontier Institute News: “New technology is helping scientists map the ocean floor in the Galapagos” <https://www.ofi.ca/news/new-technology-is-helping-scientists-map-the-ocean-floor-in-the-galapagos>

IFLSCIENCE: “Living Fossil’ Among 15 Species Found At Newly Discovered Vents In The Galápagos” <https://www.iflscience.com/living-fossil-among-15-species-found-at-newly-discovered-vents-in-the-galapagos-71799>

The Telegram: “From the bottom up: Marine geologist from Memorial University in St. John’s makes groundbreaking discoveries in Galapagos Islands”
<https://saltwire.pressreader.com/article/281560885595388>

ASTROBIOLOGY: “Away Team Report: Scientists Locate New Hydrothermal Vent Field Using State-of-the-Art Mapping Technology”
<https://astrobiology.com/2023/12/away-team-report-scientists-locate-new-hydrothermal-vent-field-using-state-of-the-art-mapping-technology.html>

MUN Gazette: “Destination: the Galapagos – Discovery of hydrothermal vent field named Tortugas in honour of famed turtle”
<https://gazette.mun.ca/research/destination-the-galapagos/>

MARINE TECHNOLOGY NEWS: “DISCOVERY: High-Res Mapping Tech Helps Find New Hydrothermal Vent Field”
<https://www.marinetechnologynews.com/news/discovery-mapping-helps-hydrothermal-632873>

LIVE SCIENCE: “Enormous hydrothermal vent field with ancient, 50-foot tall chimneys discovered near underwater volcano” <https://www.livescience.com/planet-earth/geology/enormous-hydrothermal-vent-field-with-ancient-50-foot-tall-chimneys-discovered-near-underwater-volcano>

Charles Darwin Foundation: “Scientists used high-resolution mapping technologies to find new hydrothermal vents and discover at least 15 unknown species in the Galapagos Marine Reserve.” <https://www.darwinfoundation.org/en/blog-articles/937-scientists-used-high-resolution-mapping-technologies-to-find-new-hydrothermal-vents-and-discover-at-least-15-unknown-species-in-the-galapagos-marine-reserve>

The OGM Our Great Minds: “Marine geologist makes unique discovery at famed Galapagos Islands using revolutionary ocean mapping technologies”

<https://theogm.com/2023/12/20/marine-geologist-makes-unique-discovery-at-famed-galapagos-islands-using-revolutionary-ocean-mapping-technologies/>

CBC Radio-Canada Découverte (VIDEO): “Extraire des métaux des fonds marins, une bonne idée?” (French) <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=txSC2KOUb1E>

3.6 Community Outreach

Chong Chen, "Special ways of life in deep-sea hydrothermal vent animals" 2024/02
Public seminar at the Tokyo Sea Life Park aquarium, Kasai Rinkai Park
https://www.tokyo-zoo.net/topic/topics_detail?kind=event&inst=&link_num=28323

Chong Chen, "Adaptations and lives of hot vent animals" 2024/04 Invited public seminar at the Ocean University of China, Qingdao

Neufeld, M. 2024 & 2025. Hydrothermal vents: exploring the deep sea. Blue Planet 2 (OCEA 2002). Dalhousie University, Department of Oceanography.

Daniel Ng. Mapping Pacific white skate nurseries at Iguanas-Pinguinos. ESRI Story Map: Mapping Pacific white skate nurseries at Iguanas-Pinguinos

John Jamieson: Alexander Murray Geological Society Lunch and Learn: Exploration and Discovery along the Galapagos Rift; St. John's, NL

John Jamieson: Memorial University Whale of a Day live broadcast from R/V *Falkor (too)*

Caroline Gini: Invited lecturer in: GEOG 3510 Geography of the Seas (Winter 2025): Critical metals and deep-sea mining. (Memorial University of Newfoundland)

Braga, C.H.G. Winter 2024. Guest lecture for “Introduction to Oceanography” class at Carleton University, Ottawa, Canada.

Galley, C. Spring 2024. Invited lecture at Woods Hole Oceanographic Institute, Falmouth, Massachusetts, USA.

Braga, C.H.G. Spring 2024. Science talk for European Solidarity Corps in Beaumotte-Aubertans, France.

Braga, C.H.G. Fall 2024. Guest lecture for Geological Survey of British Columbia, Victoria, Canada.

Braga, C.H.G. Fall 2024. Guest lecture for ISWAN Student Seminar Series at University of Ottawa, Ottawa, Canada.

Braga, C.H.G. Winter 2025. Guest lecture for "Oceanography" class at University of Ottawa, Ottawa, Canada.

Bethell, E. Winter 2025. Guest lecture for Department of Earth Sciences at Carleton University, Ottawa, Ontario.